

DIFFERENCES BETWEEN EUROPEAN AUSTRALIAN AND ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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ANNOTATION

The aim of this study is to examine the key features and differences of the Australian English variant (AuE). The work included an analysis of the concept of "language variant", a review of the historical background of the formation of this variant of the English language, and a study of its grammatical and lexical features. The relevance of the study is due to the growing economic, political and cultural interest in the Australian continent. As a result, it was found that the regional differences between Australian English and British English are gradually increasing, which allows us to consider it as a variant that is already beginning to assert itself as an independent language.

Key words: English language variability, colonization of the Australian continent, grammatical features of Australian English (AuE).

РАЗЛИЧИЯ МЕЖДУ ЕВРОПЕЙСКИМИ, АВСТРАЛИЙСКИМИ И АНГЛИЙСКИМИ ЯЗЫКАМИ

ANNOTATION

Целью данного исследования является изучение ключевых особенностей и различий австралийского варианта английского языка (AuE). В рамках работы был проведен анализ понятия «языковой вариант», рассмотрены исторические предпосылки формирования этого варианта английского языка, а также изучены его грамматические и лексические черты. Актуальность исследования обусловлена ростом экономического, политического и культурного интереса к Австралийскому континенту. В результате было установлено, что региональные отличия австралийского английского от британского постепенно увеличиваются, что позволяет рассматривать его как вариант, который уже начинает заявлять о себе как самостоятельный язык.

Ключевые слова: вариативность английского языка, колонизация Австралийского материка, грамматические особенности австралийского английского языка (AuE).

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the issue of language variability is drawing significant attention. The heightened interest in English language variation reflects its diversity and the unique ways it is used across different countries and regions. The relevance of this article lies in Australia's longstanding political and economic interest among European and Asian nations. For Russia, studying different variations of the English language is important, as it aids in understanding Australian culture—essential for strengthening relations and improving trade and legal frameworks.

The colonization of the Australian continent by England began in the 18th century, leading to the partial assimilation of the indigenous population and the gradual replacement of native languages with English.

This study aims to examine the main characteristics and distinctions of Australian English.

To achieve this goal, the following objectives were set: to analyze the concept of a "language variant" and to explore the primary features of Australian English. Linguist T.V. Zhrebilo defines a language variant as "a spatial, temporal, or social modification of a language, shaped by societal structure, functioning, and historical context." It is essential to differentiate a language variant from a dialect: a dialect is spoken by a limited group with shared geographic, professional, or social ties, whereas language varieties, like those of English, are beginning to establish themselves as unique languages.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

G.A. Orlov describes a language variant as "a territorially restricted version of the literary language, encompassing interdialects and regional dialects." He defines Australianisms as "linguistic elements at any level within the Australian English (AuE) system, either absent from British English (BE) or differing from the corresponding British standard across specific parameters: a) pronunciation; b) referential meaning; c) stylistic attributes (including emotional and evaluative aspects); d) lexical compatibility."

English first arrived in Australia in 1788 with the initial settlers. The formal distinction between Australian and British English was acknowledged in 1820. Australian English (AuE) developed most vigorously during the 19th century when Australia was colloquially referred to as "the big gaol." [1, 252]

Like British English, in Australian English the verbs "to spell" and "to smell" have irregular past simple and past participle forms, taking the forms "spelt" and "smelt" respectively. However, like American English, Australians are more likely to pronounce numbers such as 1100 as "eleven hundred" rather than "one thousand one hundred".

The Macquarie Dictionary of Australian English was first published in 1981, and updated editions of the dictionary are widely used around the world. In 1999, Oxford University Press, in collaboration with the Australian National University, published the Oxford Dictionary of Australian English. Many Australianisms are beginning to be recognised in other varieties of English. One notable example is the word "outback", which is used to describe a remote place. The word "barbie" replaces the noun "barbecue". [2, 106]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Consider Australian English as an example. I'm originally from the United States and moved to Australia over seven years ago. I remember my first trip to buy shampoo at what I thought would be a "drugstore." When I searched "Drugstores" on Google Maps, nothing came up. That's when I learned that in Australia, they're called chemists or pharmacies. So, I located the closest one, selected my shampoo, and headed to the checkout. The cashier asked me about my day ... or so I thought! Even though we both spoke English, I struggled to understand her accent and some of the expressions she was using after only one day in Australia.

Like many native English speakers, I had assumed the differences in our English versions would be minor and easy to overlook. However, it's essential for both native speakers and learners to realize that these differences can be both challenging and entertaining!

When comparing British and Australian accents, both generally adhere to received pronunciation (RP). Moreover, Australian English is non-rhotic, meaning that speakers, like the British, do not pronounce the /r/ sound unless it's followed by a vowel. For example:

- mar /mɑ:/

- marring /'mɑ:riŋ/

Why, then, does the American accent retain the pronounced /r/ sound, unlike other English varieties? This distinction arose because British settlers in North America were largely from the working class, while those in the UK increasingly adopted the elite's pronunciation style.

In terms of vowels, Australian speakers often elongate vowel sounds. For instance, the word *beard* might be pronounced as /bɪ:d/. The pronunciation of the letter "t" varies as well, sometimes following British English, where the /t/ sound can be dropped, and other times resembling the North American pronunciation, where it sounds closer to a /d/.

Australian and British English now share similar spelling conventions, but in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, American spelling was more common. This is why the Australian Labor Party spells "Labor" without a "u." British spelling norms were established after the *Concise Oxford English Dictionary* was introduced in the 1920s, leading to the use of endings like *-ise*, *-yse*, and *-ence* in Australia, rather than the American *-ize*, *-yze*, and *-ense*. [3, 45]

The Australian English vocabulary is uniquely rich in terms for local flora and fauna, influenced by indigenous Aboriginal languages. The Australian National University provides examples of words borrowed from these languages, such as:

- Kangaroo
- Koala
- Wombat
- Boomerang
- Numba

Australian English has also incorporated words from both American and British English. For instance, in both the US and Australia, you'll find "zucchinis" and "eggplants," while in the UK and Australia, "cilantro" and "arugula" are common terms in stores.[4, 65]

Australian English includes many unique terms that aren't found in other English varieties:

- Cobber – friend
- Battler – a working-class person struggling to make ends meet
- Bludger – a lazy person

CONCLUSION

The formation of the Australian variety of English under the influence of historical, geographical and social factors was a natural process. The differences between Australian and British English certainly go beyond simple dialect differences. Australian English has become a national variant of the modern English literary language, similar to British and American English. Language differences are mainly concentrated in areas of greatest significance to Australian society.

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